

PHOTOVOLTAIC SOLAR ENERGY: GENERATIONS, TECHNOLOGY, APPLICATIONS AND SCOPE IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

It is hard to be believe a single moment in our life with electrical energy. This electrical energy can be generated from coal, burning fossil fuels, petroleum, natural gases etc. This energy sources are known as non-renewable sources as they are available in fixed quantity in nature. They are also responsible for environmental pollution and global warming. Therefore, it is always possible to provide alternative sources of this kind of energy. Some of these sources are tidal energy, wind energy, hydrothermal energy, bio-energy and solar energy. But out of all of these sources, solar energy is particularly very interesting because sun is always there to exist in future also. The other advantage of solar energy is that it is a clean and green source of energy. It does not leave any carbon residues and freely available to common people so, no issue of pollution and global warming. The device which is used to convert solar energy into electrical energy is known as photovoltaic (PV) cell. These PV cells can be fabricated using different technology so it is important to learn and understand the working principle, how to fabricate and test the solar cell by different technology developed from time to time. In this paper, various PV cell technologies are discussed and comparison is done between them. India which is 5th largest economy of the world, have lots of scopes for solar energy and recently it replaced Italy to become 3rd most producer of solar energy in the world. Therefore, in the second half of paper, challenges, scopes, initiatives and schemes are discussed in respect of India.

Keywords: Solar Energy, Photovoltaic Cell, Renewable Source, Photovoltaic Cell Technology.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The one of important component in development of human being in modern time is electricity. It is hard to survive life for even a single day without electricity so it is necessary to produce electricity using different sources and technologies. Two sources of generating electricity are renewable and non renewable sources. Coal, natural gas, biomass are few examples of renewable sources whereas hydrothermal energy, bio-energy and solar energy are the example of non renewable sources. But out of all of these sources, solar energy is particularly very interesting because sun is always readily available to stay alive in future also. The use of electrical energy is continuously increases over the last few decades so it is necessary to produce this kind of energy using renewable sources as they do not cause any environmental pollution as well as global warming. One of the most widely and popular renewable source is solar energy which can be used to generate electrical energy. The device which is used to convert solar energy into electrical energy is called photovoltaic (PV) cell.

1.1. Construction of Photovoltaic Cell:

The basic building block of a solar cell comprises of two type semiconductors namely N-type and P-type semiconductor material. These two types' materials are processed to conduct electrode to accumulate current. One of N-type material is conducting in nature and P-type material is not fully covered because sun radiations are not fully choked-up. An antireflective coating is also there as the nature of semiconductors is reflective. Mechanical shocks are avoided by keeping whole arrangement inside a thin glass. When the photons strike the surface of the solar cell then the electron-hole pairs are released, generating a flow of electric current.

A PV cell produces half volt voltage and when these cells are arranged in definite order, higher voltage can be generated. When solar panels are collected in particular sequence, it is known as solar array which is used to produce electricity. Fig. 1 shows the construction of solar cell [1].

Fig.1. Constructional diagram and symbol of Photovoltaic cell [1]

1.2. Working Principle of PV cell:

Photovoltaic Cell works on the principle of photovoltaic effect coined by French physicist Alexandre-Edmond Becquerel in year 1839 [2]. As illustrated in fig.1, when it is exposed to light energy, a voltage difference is established due to the flow of excess holes and electronics. Thus, two semiconductor acts as voltage source creating electric field at the junction. The current produced depends on the intensity of light energy.

Some of the commonly used materials used in the construction of solar cells are silicon, indium phosphide, gallium arsenide and copper indium selenide. A general photovoltaic system consists of solar panel, charge controller, battery and inverter as shown in fig. 2. Some of applications where solar energy is used are satellites, water pumps, street light, airport and agriculture.

Fig.2. Solar Panel System Components

2. COMPARISON OF VARIOUS PHOTOVOLTAIC CELL TECHNOLOGY

PV cell uses solar energy to generate electrical energy by converting solar radiation to electric current. PV cell are fabricated using different material & technology during the past few decade. PV technologies are improving a lot during the last few decades in terms of efficiency, accuracy, and quality of PV design. At present, demand of solar energy is increasing in the world; therefore, PV cell industry is growing with different PV technologies with varying efficiency. PV cell can be fabricated using different types of materials and classification is done in different categories. Silicon is most widely used material for manufacturing of single crystalline, polycrystalline and amorphous PV cells [3-4]. It is well known that many technologies are used in fabrication of PV cells. These technologies may use non-conventional manufacturing methods for fabrication of PV cells. PV cells can be classified into four major generations with their evolution.

2.1 First Generation PV cells: In this generation, PV cells involve technologies based on mono-crystalline, poly-crystalline and Gallium Arsenide (GaAS). They are made using single silicon crystal or grains of silicon consisting of many crystals. The most important advantage of these PV cells are high efficiency and have higher share in solar cell market till date although they have higher manufacturing cost [5]. Gallium arsenide is most popularly used for multi-junction PV cells consisting of multiple p-n junctions fabricated using different semiconductor materials.

The first generation PV cells are classified into three categories:

1. Mono crystalline silicon PV cells
2. Polycrystalline silicon PV cells
3. Gallium Arsenide PV cells

2.1.1. Mono crystalline silicon PV cells

These cells can be fabricated by inserting small seed silicon crystal melt into a crucible, pulling it upwards to get a single crystal. This single crystal is known as ingot whose crystal properties such as orientation, lattice parameters and electronics related properties are uniform.

They are the most widely used base materials in PV cell industry. Bridgman-Stockbarger method is other way to produce a single crystal [6].

2.1.2 Polycrystalline silicon PV cell:

The polycrystalline Si wafer consists of crystal grains oriented randomly is known as multi-crystal PV cell. The biggest advantages of this PV cell are that they involve less energy in their fabrication and greenhouse effect is much less as compared to mono-crystal PV cell. However, they have efficiency less than mono-crystal Si PV cell. The efficiency of a given cell is 19.9% and this is due to inferior material class due to grain boundaries and defects, and the high concentration of impurities [12].

2.1.3 Gallium Arsenide PV cells:

Gallium Arsenide (GaAs) cells are used in fabrication of multi-junction cells which consists of multiple junctions with different semiconductor materials and they have high performance capability. This type of cell is constructed with Ga and As using vapor phase reaction with low pressure and high temperature. As these cells utilize multiple semiconducting materials which permits board range of wavelength absorption; thus improving energy conversion efficiency of these cell [13]. These cells have obtained efficiencies in the range of 18.4-28.8% in lab depending upon crystalline structure or thin layer. Table 1 shows the comparison of first generation PV cells with different parameters.

Table 1: Comparison of First Generation PV cells

Parameters	Mono crystalline silicon PV cells	Polycrystalline silicon PV cells	Gallium Arsenide PV cells
Photovoltaic technologies cell	Mono-crystalline silicon (m-si) wafer	polycrystalline silicon (p-si) wafer	Gallium arsenide (GaAs) wafers
Images			
Fabrication Process	Czochralski process	Czochralski process	Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD)
Efficiency	15-24 %	10-18 %	26-29.1%
Advantages	Mono-crystalline solar cell is generally used due to its high-efficiency level as compared to the multi-crystalline cell [14] Occupy a small space	Cost-effective as compared to the mono-crystalline module.	Better efficiency compared to mono and poly crystalline PV cells.
Disadvantages	(c-Si) technology is too expensive for large-scale operation [15]. (c-Si) modules have a weak interaction with light as Si is an indirect bandgap semiconductor [14].	Less efficiency than the mono-crystalline module as it is made of impure Si [16]. Consume a larger area [17].	quite expensive

2.2. Second Generation PV Cells:

The second generation PV cells are also known as thin films PV cells and they are fabricated to cut down the cost of PV panels. The second generation PV cells are less costly as they use thin films of Silicon of approximately about 1 μm as compared to wafer based technology used in first generation PV cells. R.Chittick was the first person to develop amorphous silicon deposited thin film PV cell [18]. The biggest advantage of these cells is its fabrication in large size and mounting on curved surface by utilizing suitable substrate. Some key characteristics about second generation solar cells are illustrated in Fig.3.

Fig.3. Key Characteristics of 2nd Generation PV cell

The second generation PV cells are classified into 4 categories depending upon the material used in their fabrication. Table 2 shows comparison of different types of 2nd generation PV cells.

Table 2: Comparison of 2nd Generation PV cells

Parameters	Amorphous Silicon	Copper Indium Gallium Di-Selenide [CIGS]	Gallium Arsenide PV cells	Cadmium Tellurium
Material used in fabrication	Amorphous Silicon	Copper Indium Gallium Di-Selenide	Gallium arsenide (GaAs) wafers	Cadmium Tellurium
Efficiency	15-24 %	10-18 %	26-29.1%	
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cheaper than Silicon based wafer Technology. Available in different size and shapes. Degradation with environment condition. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher efficiency than crystalline -Si PV cells. Low cost. Fabrication is easy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High resistivity to heat damage. High absorption coefficient due to direct BG material. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy receiving capacity from sun spectrum is higher compared to Si-crystalline PV cell.
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficiency is lower compared to 1st Generation PV cells. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indium and Gallium are not available in abundance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly expensive Toxic material & harmful. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tellurium is limited in supply. Cadmium is highly poisonous.

2.1.2. Amorphous silicon PV cell

The best-developed thin-film solar cell technology is amorphous silicon and commercially used since 1980. Amorphous silicon does not pose a crystalline structure and it is fabricated into thin films instead of si-wafers. Indeed, the first major commercial technology used in fabrication of thin films was amorphous silicon. Carlson and Wronski at Radio Corporation of America (RCA) Research Laboratories devised the first amorphous silicon (a-Si) based PV cell with only 2.4% of conversion efficiency [18]. Amorphous Si is the most widely used inactive layer in silicon based PV cells as it has high absorption coefficient. Plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD) is used in construction of this type of cell and used to generate silicon-thin films. In this type of cell, base is made up of plastic or stainless steel. Deposition of amorphous silicon one over the other makes a thin layer of amorphous silicon PV cells which resulted in development a solar panel. The controlling of deposition conditions within certain ranges is always needed to deposit good quality a-Si films. These cells can be used in buildings and photovoltaic power cells where thin-film applications are required. The fig. 4 illustrated the construction of this type of PV cell.

Fig.4. Constructional view of amorphous silicon PV cell

2.1.3. Copper Indium Gallium Selenide (CIGS) PV Cell

Copper gallium indium selenide (CIGS) is one of the fastest growing thin film photovoltaic solar cells. They are sandwiched between conductive layers and deposited on substrate made up with glass, plastic, steel or aluminium. Low temperature coefficient, High absorption, tandem design possibility and protective layer are some of the technological advantages of these solar cells. CIGS PV solar cells are made up with semiconductor material having band gap between 1.0 to 1.7 eV depending upon the proportion of the elements in the compound [19].

2.1.4. Gallium Arsenide PV cell

The multi-junction solar cells which are also known as tandem solar cells consist of contain multiple thin films. They are developed for special applications such satellites and house exploration. For an example, a triple junction cell may compose of semiconductors Gallium arsenide (GaAs), Germanium (Ge) and Gallium Indium diphosphate (GaInP₂). The selected semiconductors are able to immerse whole solar spectrum such that electricity can be generated from the maximum amount of the solar power as attainable. The maximum efficiency that is achieved so far by triple junction solar cells is 42.3% but this is done at cost of complexity and multiple fabrications cost [20]. The high cost and higher maintenance cost to performance ratio of these cells are the biggest constrained in their use.

2.1.5. Cadmium Tellurium PV cell

Cadmium Telluride PV solar cell are also thin film cells and made from compound cadmium telluride with a band gap of 1.45 eV as main energy producing layer and other surrounding layers for electricity conduction and collection. The biggest disadvantage of this cell is use of cadmium which is toxic in nature thus fabrication and disposal both difficult and greatest concern for environmental concern. Moreover, the efficiency of these PV cells is less as compared to crystalline Silicon PV cell. The maximum efficiency is 18.3 % for Cadmium Telluride PV solar cell [20].

2.2. Third-Generation Solar Cell:

Third generation solar cell which is not commercially-advanced 'emerging' technologies and these are based on chemical compounds, organic polymers and nano crystalline films. These cells are capable of high efficiency while keeping production cost reasonably low [21]. The solar cells implemented with thin-film technologies have dramatically impact the economics of utilization of solar cells thus making solar energy accessible to every fold of world and in cheapest fashion in future energy production.

The major aim of these solar cell technologies is to produce highly efficient devices at less expense. Although, most of the research and development in this generation is done at laboratories conditions and therefore they are not commercially used. Still majority of solar cell technologies share in market is captured by first- and second-generation solar cells. Classification of third generation solar cell can be done based on several technologies and can be sensitized depending upon dye-sensitized material, quantum dots and perovskite sensitized solar cells. The types of third generation solar cells depending upon different varieties of materials are shown in fig. 5.

2.2.1 Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells

The most exciting technological advancements in the world of solar cells are dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC) also known as Gratzel cells after scientist Micheal Gratzel who discovered these cells in 1991 at UC Berkeley [22]. The biggest advantage of DSSC is its potential to become major energy source in future because it is transparent and less expensive than other generations of solar cells. One of the major material used in its fabrication is nano-sized TiO₂ (titanium dioxide) porous film electrodes which is a large bandgap semiconductor that is mostly used in paints, toothpaste, and other day-to-day applications. The most essential elements of a DSSC are photoanode, sensitizer, and electrolyte and counter electrode [23]. Figure 1.5 depicts the typical structure and operation principle of DSSC.

Fig. 6 The structure of dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) [23]

One of the main components of DSSC is photo-anode which provides the corridor for electron transportation and energy conversion efficiency of the DSSC is determined. The photoanode is developed using semiconductor nanostructures. Numerous semiconductor oxides such as ZnO, SnO₂, WO₃ and TiO₂ are used as a material for photo-anode which is placed on transparent glass with dye-sensitized. Out of these semiconductor oxides, TiO₂ has more popular due to its low cost, easy availability, compatibility and lack of toxicity. The peculiar property of TiO₂ is that it has wide energy bandgap which can be existed in three rutile, anatase and brookite crystalline phase. Some researchers believe that ZnO (Zinc oxide) is the most suitable alternative for TiO₂. The injection of electrons into conduction band of semiconductor takes place due to photo-excitation of the dye. The dye is regenerated in electrolyte containing a redox couple (I⁻) and reduction of I⁻ with electrons are passed through external circuit. The output voltage produced under illumination is nothing but the difference between energy bandgap in semiconductor and the redox potential of the electrolyte. The overall outcome is the conversion of light into electricity without any chemical transformation. Therefore, DSSC is also a re-generative type photo electrochemical cell. The biggest challenges in DSSC are poor conversion efficiency estimated theoretically around 32% but highest achieved till date is 13% and cell stability. The other major issue with DSSC is cost of material and need to be short out in future [24].

2.2.2 Quantum Dots Photovoltaic Cells

A Quantum Dots Photovoltaic Cell is fabricated using tiny particles called as quantum dots which are few nanometers in size (usually 1 to 10 nm) with size dependent optical, mechanical and electrical properties which typically not practical in bulk material. These tiny particles are used for absorbing incident sun light for Photovoltaic effect. Quantum dots with 5-6 nm in diameter emit longer wavelengths with color and smaller quantum dots with 2-3 nm in diameters emit smaller wavelengths but particular color and size depends on the exact symphony of quantum dots. Some of commonly used methods for synthesis of these cells are Electrochemical Carbonization, Laser Ablation, Microwave Irradiation and Hydrothermal Treatment. These types of PV cells are considered as derivative of Dye Sensitized Photovoltaic solar cells and they have higher ability to absorb more photon due to its tunable energy band gap with theoretical efficiency of 44% [25]. Some of advantages of these cells are power to weight ratio, better efficiency, low power consumption and versatility etc.

2.2.3 Perovskite solar cell

Perovskite Solar Cells fall under 3rd generation solar cells which contribute largely in solar energy generation because of their high Performance Conversion Efficiency (PCE) and compatibility with other process. The name Perovskite was invented after a Russian mineralogist, L.A. Perovski, for identical crystal structure with calcium titanium oxide (CaTiO₃) having stoichiometry of three-dimensional structure ABX₃, where A and B are smaller and larger cations and anions exist in X [26]. Fig. shows three-dimensional (3D) and two-dimensional (2D) schematic structure as well as unit cell arrangement for perovskite material.

Fig. 5. Three-dimensional (3D) and two-dimensional (2D) schematic structure and unit cell of Perovskite Solar Cell [26]

The biggest advantage of these materials is their availability in abundant in nature and they show wide range of properties, importance and applications compared to any other PV technology. These PV cells have two types of structures depending upon the architecture, namely conventional and an inverted PSC structure. In conventional structure, TiO₂ and n-type semiconductors are used where as in an inverted PSC structure, p-type poly (3,4-ethylene dioxythiophene)-poly(styrene sulfonate) (PEDOT: PSS) are used. Fig. shows these two types of structures.

Fig. 6. Conventional and Inverted Structure of Perovskite solar cell [27]

Some of commonly used perovskites materials currently used are CH₃NH₃PbI₃, CH₃NH₃-PbBr₃ and the mixed halide system, CH₃NH₃PbI_{3-x}Cl_x. These materials are used in Perovskite solar because of their low recombination losses, low cost and low exciton binding energy. A perovskite solar cell with CH₃NH₃PbI₃ perovskite SCs fabricated utilizing ZnO NCs as photocathode reported PCE of 15.7% [27]. Some of disadvantages of these solar cells are excessive use of lead is big dispute in its commercial use and V-I hysteresis between different types of biasing. Therefore, future research will focus on the reducing halide defects, inclusion of 2D perovskites and inorganic charge-extraction layers utilization and lastly charge carrier transport mechanism understanding.

2.2.4 Tandem & Multi-junction Photovoltaic Cells

A Tandem photovoltaic solar cell is fabricated with different materials with varying bandgaps mounted into a single structure so that it can use maximum sunlight to generate electricity. It is illustrated in [28] that 86% of solar spectrum can be utilized just by connecting cells of different bandgaps. It is important to maintain a temperature below 150 degree Celsius while manufacturing these cells. The schematic diagram of Tandem solar cell is shown in fig. 7.

Fig.6. Shows schematic diagram of TSC, (a) mechanically stacked 4T, (b) monolithically integrated 2T, and (c) optical splitting of the solar spectrum [28]

It is possible to achieve efficiency beyond 26% using tandem configuration and it is also possible to attain efficiency greater than 30% with thin film tandem solar cell configuration.

The practically achieved conversion efficiency of various solar cells is still short of Shockley-Queisser (S-Q) limit which is approximately 33% [29]. Now, it is always desirable to gain more of the untapped and abundance power of sun's energy beyond (S-Q) limit and this can be achieved by multi junction solar cell (MJSC) proposed in 1955 by connecting multiple p-n semiconductor junctions connected in series with highest energy bandgap at top and thereafter decreasing bandgaps below [30]. MJSC can be fabricated with multiple junctions from two to six junction's solar cells. Sometimes, MJSC are also called tandem cells if they are fabricated with two materials with different values of energy bandgaps. The most popular and widely used MJSC is a triple junction solar cell consisting three semiconductor absorbers detached by a tunneling junction. MJSC has achieved the maximum light conversion efficiency with 47.1% under concentrated illumination of 143 suns and 39.2% under 1 Sun illumination by piling 6-junctions [31]. Presently, MJSCs are utilized in space missions for terrestrial concentrated photovoltaic systems.

2.2.5. Organic Solar Cells (OSC)

Low cost, light weight, flexibility, non-toxic nature and appropriateness for large scale processing have developed interest of researchers in organic solar cells (OSC). These advancements in OSC with high performance active layer materials, various electrodes and novel structures increases the PCE thus making it possible for practical applications [26]. National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) reveals that PCE of OSCs is increasing rapidly yielding PCE of 19.2% as per [27]. Major applications of inorganic cells are in rooftops and open fields whereas OSCs can find its applications in windows, screens, smart glasses, automobiles and charges of electronics appliances such as mobile and laptops.

The OSCs first generation with a single active layer, which was sandwiched between two electrodes with different work functions showed poor PCE below 0.1% as it was not able to achieve efficient dissociation of excitations [28]. Tang in 1986 discovered OSC having PCE of around 1% with a bilayer hetero-junction structure with copper phthalocyanine as donor (D) and perylene tetracarboxylic derivate as acceptor (A) as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. A bilayer heterojunction & Bulk heterojunction (BHJ) OSCs solar cell

Bulk heterojunction (BHJ) OSCs were invented in 1995 by mixing donor and acceptor to act as the active layer. BHJ structure was the first major breakthrough in OSCs with PCE of over 18% thus a new era of promising technology in this field starts. Numerous types of more complex materials for donor and acceptor have been discovered with improved optical and electrical characteristics. One of improvement was ternary and tandem OSCs which are gaining popularity with the great process attained in materials which absorbs light. Combining good quality plastics with those of semiconductors, optical absorption coefficients with large value and low cost fabrication are some of the major characteristics of OSCs. BHC structure is preferred in fabrication over bilayer due very less diffusion path lengths and fabricated using thermal evaporation and inkjet printing techniques [28]. It is very difficult to achieve high efficiency in OSCs due to lesser and in-effective transport of excitons, charge carriers and poor stability.

2.3. FOURTH GENERATION:

The emphasis on efficient and stable solar cells has given confidence to researchers to develop fourth generation solar cells. These solar cells are fabricated by combining all the benefits exhibited by previous generation solar cells. They are also known as hybrid solar cells because they have ability to include inorganic materials with organic materials [27]. The most commonly used materials used in their making are metal oxides and metal nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes and graphene and its derivatives [28].

Various 2D materials such as molybdenum disulphide (MoS₂), graphene, tungsten disulphide (WS₂) and tungsten diselenide (WSe₂) becoming popular and gaining immense interest in fourth generation solar cells because they have excellent optical properties, slim size and light weight. These 2D materials are from the family of transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs). The other materials used in fabrication of these cells are graphene and their derivatives. These materials have flexibility, mechanical strength, tunable band gaps, better carrier mobility, quantum hall effect and magnetic anisotropy attributes to their quantum confinement [29-30].

Due to these properties, 2D materials have been used in the designing of various solar cells as they can used as a transparent electrode, e-transport material, an active layer and transparent diffusion barrier. Graphene and its derivatives are used in designing of solar cells due to its tight package style, 2-D honeycomb structure along with protecting photovoltaic's cells from environmental degradation as shown in Fig.

Fig. (a) Honeycomb hexagonal structure of graphene. **(b)** Structure of 2D materials in terms of the metal coordination (top), and stacking sequence (bottom)

2.3.1 Graphene, and their Derivatives

Graphene and its derivatives which is considered as a nanomaterial of the future, provide an excellent flexibility and affordability in fourth generation solar cells. High conductive graphene is used in flexible photovoltaic cells making it suitable for use in selective charge-taking element and electrode interlayer material [31]. Graphene has significant role as a transparent electrode, charges transport material and interfacial buffer layer thus making it suitable for photovoltaic material in the last two decades. Other property is protecting the device from environmental degradation with 2D lattice structure and increases environmental stability.

Fig. shows a graphene-silicon solar cell with a Schottky junction. It consists of graphene sheets fabricated using chemical vapour deposition (CVD) on nickel films deposited on pre-patterned Si/SiO₂ substrates with an effective area of 0.1–0.5 cm². This graphene sheet constitutes a coating on the exposed n-Si substrate which creates a Schottky junction.

Fig. 4 Graphene–silicon Schottky junction solar cell. **(a)** Graphene based Solar Cell Cross-sectional view, **(b)** schematic illustration of the device configuration[32]

Bottom-up and top-bottom are the two most common methods for graphene synthesis. In top-bottom method, graphite is the initial material and the objective is to intercalate and exfoliate it into graphene sheets by solid, liquid, or electrochemical exfoliation. In bottom-up method, graphene is produced from molecular precursors using chemical vapor deposition (CVD) or epitaxial growth. The various properties such as structure, morphology, and attributes of the resulting graphene depend on the manufacturing process [33, 34].

Therefore, graphene and its derivatives is most popular and promising field of research in the last two decades since they are in the initial stage of research and development.

Hydrophilicity is one of the biggest disadvantages of graphene which affects the device design processed in solution but this can be overcome by modifying the surface using non-covalent chemical functionalization. Due to high mechanical strength and flexibility as well as excellent conductivity, it can be utilised in plastics and optoelectronics thus paves the way for cheaper graphene layer [35].

3. CURRENT & FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS OF PHOTOVOLTAIC CELL IN INDIA

3.1. Present Scenario and Challenges of Solar Energy in India

In India, almost 300 sunny days in year emits radiations equivalent to 5000 trillion KWh per year. It was decided that 100 GW of solar power will generated out of total 175 GW of different renewable energy. India has so far installed 43 GW of solar power in different parts of India. The largest solar power plant of India was inaugurated by Mr Narender Modi, Prime Minister of India in the Jwad area at the Diken in Madhya Pradesh and this was one of the steps in achieve and spreading solar energy in India. However, to achieve the target of 100 GW of solar power, there are numerous challenges are there in India.

Therefore, solar power capacity in India has tremendous scope for replacing to other non-renewable energies. Solar energy can be utilized for variety of purposes such as heating, drying, cooking, cars, ships, satellites or generation of electricity as our country is the most populated country in the world. The other biggest reason for solar energy utilization in India is that our country is going to be kerosene free in coming years. In spite of these advantages, India is also facing many challenges in solar energy generation and its implementation in various sections of the country. Table 1 listed the most notable Solar Energy Challenges in India.

Table 1: Solar Energy Challenges in India

Challenges	Reason for facing challenge
Large Capital Investment	The cost of capital investment is 11% in India whereas it is only 5% in China
Complicated Manufacturing Process	Manufacturing process is technology intensive which is not possible in India.
Large crunch in raw material supply	Manufacturer in India suffers lack of raw material supply for manufacturing solar panel.
Frequent change in Solar Cell Technology	Solar Cell Technology witnesses up-gradation in Solar cell Technology in every 8-10 months thus making it tough for manufacturer to upgrade their machinery and equipment.
Lack of Domestic Manufacturing of Solar Parts	The domestic manufacturing industry of solar PV cells and modules is severely lacking in India due to the lack of infrastructure, skilled workforce and high cost of production.
Production Barrier	Lithium which is the primary raw material in manufacturing of SV cell is imported from china hence India depends upon china for production of SV cells. Lithium which is used in manufacturing for PV solar Cells is imported from china.
Technological barriers	It is tough to meet out the conditions and barriers of latest technological manufacturing techniques of SV cells in India.
Waste Management	It is predicted that solar waste grows up to 1.8 million tonnes by 2050. In India, e-waste rules are not drafted so far hence it will be tough to dispose-off the large solar waste every year.

4. STEPS TO ENHANCE SOLAR ENERGY GENERATION IN INDIA

India which is the second-largest market in Asia for new solar PV capacity has set a striving target to achieve of 175 GW worth of renewable energy by the end of 2022, 500 GW up to 2030. The portion of various renewable energies in production of 175 GW is shown in Fig.

Fig. Renewable Energy Target of India to be completed by 2022

Out of these, 100 GW of energy will be generated from solar and used in many areas with different applications. Solar energy can be used by millions of people in India for their cooking, home lighting and electricity in an eco friendly manner. Use of solar energy will also helps rural women and girls in reducing grind, minimizing lung and eye diseases and finally uplifting the standard of living as well as economic standard. Further, solar energy can also be utilized as a significant pillar in the grid connected power generation while supporting the agenda of sustainable growth across the country.

National Institute of Solar Energy (NISE) has studied that India can lead the world in solar energy and has launched India's National Action Plan on climate change with National Solar Mission (NSM) on 11th January, 2010. NSM implement National Action Plan in three phases through several steps including Solar Park Scheme, Central Public Sector Undertakings (CPSUs) scheme for grid connected solar PV power projects, and Viability Gap Funding (VGF). The primary objective of NSM is to promote India as a global leader solar energy by creating the policy conditions for solar technology diffusion across the country within time frame as well as proper implementation policies.

Thus, to meet out these demands and spreading the utilization of solar energy in India, Government of India has started various schemes and initiatives to encourage generation of solar energy in India such as solar park scheme, Grid Connected Solar power generation, Roof Top solar scheme etc. Government has taken several steps for promotion of solar energy in the country. These include:

1. Promoting Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) up to 100 percent under the automatic route.
2. Waiver of Inter State Transmission System (ISTS) charges for inter-state sale of solar and wind power for projects to be commissioned by 30th June 2025.
3. Declaration of trajectory for Renewable Purchase Obligation (RPO) up to the year 2029-30.
4. Notification of standards for deployment of solar photovoltaic system/devices.
5. Setting up of Project Development Cell for attracting and facilitating investments.

6. Standard Bidding Guidelines for tariff based competitive bidding process for procurement of Power from Grid Connected Solar PV and Wind Projects.
7. Government has issued orders that power shall be dispatched against Letter of Credit (LC) or advance payment to ensure timely payment by distribution licensees to RE generators.
8. Notification of Promoting Renewable Energy through Green Energy Open Access Rules 2022.
9. Notification of “The electricity (Late Payment Surcharge and related matters) Rules 2002 (LPS rules).
10. Launch of Green Term Ahead Market (GTAM) to facilitate sale of Renewable Energy power including solar power through exchanges.

Some of related initiatives and schemes spreading the utilization of solar energy are listed in table 22.

Table 2: Various Schemes initiated by GOI

Name of the Scheme	Year of Launch	Purpose of the Scheme	Application area
Solar Park Scheme	December 2014	Building a number of solar parks	To set up at least 25 Solar Parks and Ultra Mega Solar Power Projects
Rooftop Solar Scheme	February 19, 2019	Harness solar power by installing solar panels on the roof of houses.	Implementing Grid-connected Rooftop Solar Scheme and small SPV power generating plants among the residential, community, institutional, industrial and commercial establishments.
National Solar Mission	11 January 2010	Initiative of the Government of India and State Governments to promote renewable energy	Set the target of 20,000 MW of Grid connected and 2000 MW of Off-grid capacity by 2022.
SRISTI Scheme	December 2017	to promote rooftop solar power projects in India	To promote rooftop solar power projects in India. smaller residential rooftop systems
International Solar Alliance	30 th November 2015	an action-oriented, member-driven, collaborative platform	Increasing deployment of solar energy technologies.
PM Kisan Urja Suraksha evam Utthaan Mahabhiyan (PM-KUSUM)	March 2019	to support installation of off-grid solar pumps in rural areas and reduce dependence on grid, in grid-connected areas	Solar energy-based power plants (SEPP) of capacity 500 kW to 2 MW will be setup by individual farmers/ group of farmers/ cooperatives/ panchayats/ Farmer Producer Organisations (FPO)/Water User associations (WUA)
Modified Special Incentive Package Scheme (M-SIPS)	July 2012 & Revision of MSIPS in July, 2015	offers a 20-25 per cent subsidy for investments in capital expenditure for setting up a manufacturing facility	to promote large scale manufacturing in the country and attract investments in Electronics System Design and Manufacturing (ESDM) Industries.
Atal Jyoti Yojana (AJAY)	Phase-I September 2016 & Phase-II December 2018	the installation of solar street lighting (SSL) systems in states	solar street lights (SSLs)
PM Surya Ghar Muft Bijli Yojana	February 15, 2024.	Solar panels are installed in houses under this scheme.	To supply power to households and additional money for excess electricity output.

Due to these initiatives and scheme launched by Government of India, our country stands 5th in Solar PV deployment across the global with solar power installed capacity around 70.10 GW in 2023.

Recently, India achieved the 5th global position in solar power deployment by surpassing Italy. Solar power capacity has increased by more than 11 times in the last five years from 2.6 GW in March 2014 to 30 GW in July 2019. Presently, solar tariffs in India are very competitive and have achieved grid parity.

CONCLUSION

The Indian government has taken several initiatives and policies to propel the solar energy market, including, SARAL Index, PM KUSUM Floating solar plants in Gujarat, and ISA in Haryana. Solar energy, with its low carbon footprint, can be a potential substitute for conventional energy sources and can help India fulfill its commitments under the INDCs and Panchamrit proposals at COP 26.

The Government has also provided **financial incentives** for expansion of solar energy. These include: **(a)** The Government has provided a 10-year **tax exemption** for solar energy projects; **(b)** **Waiver of Inter-State Transmission System (ISTS) charges** for inter-state sale of solar and wind power for projects to be commissioned by 30th June 2025; **(c)** The Ministry of New and Renewable Energy provides **30% subsidy** to most solar powered items such as solar lamps and solar heating systems. It has further extended its subsidy scheme to solar-powered cold storages; **(d)** The Government has allowed 100% Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) under the automatic route; **(e)** Government has issued orders that power shall be dispatched against Letter of Credit (LC) or advance payment to **ensure timely payment by distribution licensees to renewable energy generators**; **(f)** Government has also launched Green funds like the National Clean Energy and Environmental Fund, Green Masala Bond etc.

The Government has also undertaken initiatives for **international collaboration**. India is the founding member of the [International Solar Alliance \(ISA\)](#) which is headquartered in India. India has proposed the idea of “[One Sun, One World, One Grid](#)” as a means of tapping into the copious solar electricity available on a worldwide scale.

5. CNCLUSIONS

A device which converts solar radiation into electrical energy called photovoltaic solar cell is getting due importance in the present day scenario as sun is ultimate source of pure and unlimited solar energy. Therefore, many photovoltaic solar cells were developed in the past to fulfil the demand of electrical energy and still the journey is continuing. Various photovoltaic cell technologies are developed across the world in last few decades. In this paper, an exhausted review of various generations of PV Solar cells along with technologies is done along with their advantages and disadvantages. In the second half of the paper, coverage is done on scopes, initiatives and schemes on increasing the generation of solar power in India. Due to various schemes and initiatives taken by Government of India, our country is now ranked fourth globally for the production of solar energy with goal of achieving 450 GW of Renewable Energy by 2030 with the sunlight coming on the surface of Earth.

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